
Proof of Code: A Licensing Model for Usability Using NFTs.

Abstract:

As the software development landscape evolves, the need for more flexible and secure licensing models is growing. Traditional licensing approaches often focus on the sale of intellectual property rights or impose limitations on usage. This paper introduces a novel "Proof of Code" model for licensing software through Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs), focusing on a NFT inspired royalty model for the usability of code rather than the sale or transfer of its proprietary blueprints. By linking usability royalties to NFTs, developers can retain ownership of the core intellectual property while granting access to functionality, allowing for code evolution, innovation, and use without selling or revealing proprietary concepts. This model introduces a royalty principles while preserving control over key elements of software architecture and digital genome IP, while blueprints evolve in norms of machine evolution.

1. Introduction

The licensing of software has traditionally been tied to time-based or material-based models, or alternatively, to open-source licenses that require the release of full source code. These models often fail to balance the needs of innovation, commercialization, and intellectual property (IP) protection. With the rise of blockchain technologies, particularly Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs), a new model is emerging that allows software developers to preserve the proprietary nature of their code while still enabling others to utilize it.

In this paper, we propose a licensing model based on NFTs that focuses on usability of code and software features without relinquishing control over the code's architecture or digital genome. By doing so, developers can maintain ownership of their intellectual property and protect key innovations, all while fostering collaboration, evolution, and use of the code.

2. Traditional Licensing Models: Limitations

In traditional software licensing models, the two most common approaches are:

Time and Material Licensing: Developers are compensated based on the time and effort spent on the software. While this approach ensures developers are paid, it doesn't clearly define ownership or offer long-term IP protection.

Open-Source Licensing: Open-source licenses such as MIT, GPL, or Apache promote wide sharing and collaboration but often require the release of the entire codebase, including proprietary components. This can expose valuable innovations and code blueprints to potential misuse or unauthorized commercialization.

The need for a model that enables code usability without compromising proprietary concepts—such as algorithms, digital genome IP, or evolutionary blueprints—has become increasingly important. This is where the Proof of Code model powered by NFTs comes into play.

3. Proof of Code: Usability Licensing with NFTs

Proof of Code utilizes NFTs to create a system where developers can license the usability of their software, granting users permission to interact with the code in predefined ways, while keeping the underlying blueprint and intellectual property (IP) protected. The main distinction here is that the code itself remains proprietary, but access to the functionality is granted under specific licensing terms through NFTs.

3.1 How NFTs Facilitate Usability Licensing

NFTs serve as digital tokens linked to specific pieces of code or functionality. These tokens act as licenses that grant users access to certain features, use cases, or services within the software, without exposing or transferring the underlying blueprints or proprietary elements of the codebase. Features of NFTs that make them suitable for this purpose include:

Indivisibility: NFTs can represent a single, indivisible unit of code functionality. This ensures that users are granted specific rights or access tied directly to the NFT, while the original code remains unchanged.

Traceability: NFTs leverage blockchain's transparency to provide a verifiable record of usage rights and ownership without disclosing any proprietary code.

Smart Contracts: NFTs can be tied to smart contracts that automatically enforce specific terms of use. For example, access to a certain functionality or a particular version of the code can be granted based on predefined criteria encoded into the NFT.

3.2 Licensing Usability without Revealing Proprietary Code

The Proof of Code model provides a way for developers to grant usability licenses—the right to run, modify, or interact with specific functionality—while maintaining complete control over the intellectual property and the digital genome (i.e., the core digital genome, a blueprint transcribed customizable).

For instance:

Exclusive Usability: A user might be granted exclusive rights to use a certain set of features for a particular application, but they would not have access to the underlying source code or be able to transfer this functionality to another project.

Non-exclusive Usability: Multiple users might be granted access to the same code functionality under a general license, but they do not own the code and cannot modify or redistribute it.

Versioning and Evolution: Developers can release updates or evolutions of the code by minting new NFTs for the updated functionality, keeping the core blueprint protected from public access while encouraging innovation and progression within the ecosystem.

The key advantage of this model is that it allows code to evolve in a modular way, where each version or enhancement can be licensed separately, maintaining ownership of the core code and protecting digital genome IP.

4. Benefits of Proof of Code Licensing with NFTs

The Proof of Code model is a proof of code and a consensus algorithm offers numerous benefits over traditional licensing models:

Preservation of Proprietary IP: Developers can retain control over their intellectual property, including core algorithms and digital genome, while allowing others to benefit from the functionality of their code.

Flexibility in Licensing: Developers can create multiple licensing tiers (exclusive, non-exclusive, usage-based) depending on the user's needs, while ensuring that the underlying code remains protected.

Easier Enforcement: The blockchain's transparent and immutable nature allows for the automated tracking of usage rights and prevents unauthorized use or redistribution of the code.

Fostering Innovation: By licensing the usability rather than the full source code, the model allows for modular development, enabling collaborators to work on specific aspects of the software while preserving the overall integrity of the proprietary design.

Global Market Access: Like other blockchain-based technologies, NFTs are borderless, enabling global transactions and fostering collaboration and distribution across different regions and industries.

5. Challenges and Considerations

While the Proof of Code model offers a promising solution, there are challenges that need to be addressed:

Complexity in Implementation: Creating NFTs for each piece of functionality or version can be complex, especially when managing large codebases or intricate software systems.

Scalability Issues: Storing large software on the blockchain, even in an abstracted form, can become costly or inefficient. Off-chain storage with on-chain references may provide a practical solution.

Legal Frameworks: Existing legal frameworks may not fully support NFT-based licensing for software, requiring updates to copyright, IP, and contract laws to accommodate these new forms of digital licensing.

Adoption: Widespread adoption of this model will require a shift in the way software licensing is perceived and an understanding of how NFTs can enhance protection and usability of code.

6. Conclusion

The Proof of Code licensing model introduces a revolutionary way to grant usability licenses for software code through NFTs, without selling or exposing proprietary blueprints or the core digital genome IP. This approach offers developers a way to preserve ownership of their intellectual property while enabling others to leverage code functionality in a secure, transparent, and efficient manner. As blockchain technology and NFTs continue to evolve, the Proof of Code model has the potential to reshape the software licensing landscape, offering a more balanced and sustainable approach to code sharing and innovation.

References:

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